

NDAC/LO/128

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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XI

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This note discusses the impact of the Recovery mission on the Hipparcos double star reductions. Although only a small number of doubles have been simulated, it is clear that the important question is the lifetime of the mission. With 18 months of observations, quite useful results are obtained.

1. Simulations with the recovery orbit

The previous simulation software has been modified to have the satellite in the recovery orbit. As noted by Lindegren (NDAC/LO/127), it is sufficient to take the apse-node motion due to the earth's flattening (J_2) into account, otherwise, the orbit has fixed Keplerian elements (from van der Ha and Clausen). Three ground stations are assumed to be available (Odenwald, Perth and Kourou), and observations are limited to periods when the satellite is more than 10000 km above the earth. As before, occultations by earth and moon are taken into account, and no observations at all are made in the 'hibernation periods' 1990 Feb 2-Apr 9 and 1991 Sep 12-Oct 21. The beginning of observations is taken at Oct 15, 1989.

With these limitations, observations were generated in three series. In all cases, the primary magnitude was 8.5, the separation between 1 and 10 arcsec, and the magnitude difference between 0 and 4 mag. In Ser. I, 100 systems were simulated for a 24-month mission. As compared with the nominal mission, the attitude errors were increased by 50% (mean error for Ω 4.5 mas). (As a comparison, 100 systems were also simulated for a 'nominal' 24-month mission with the satellite in geostationary orbit). Ser. II includes 200 systems for 18 months ($\sigma_\Omega=6$ mas), and Ser. III another 200 systems observed for 12 months ($\sigma_\Omega=7.5$ mas). In Ser. II and III, one half of the systems (a) had a priori relative position mean errors 0.2 arcsec, the other half (b) 0.7 arcsec (as Ser. I). The corresponding figure for the primaries is 1.0 arcsec throughout.

2. Results of STDDBLs-solutions

The standard STDDBLs solution program was used, in the '2-stage' mode described in NDAC/LO/124. The C_i -parameters were chosen with standard ratios according to NDAC/LO/125, only C_4 adjusted to fit the mean S_f . When observations are available for 24 months, the solutions present few problems. A non-optimized run gave 92 good solutions, 4 (low-latitude) cases with a wrong secondary position and 4 cases with no solution (two due to a too small search-mesh for the primary position). The mean 'rms' (all five astrometric parameters) for the primaries is 2.0 mas, and the mean $S_e(pr)=8.1$. To allow a better comparison with the shorter runs, rms values for the errors in (total) primary position, primary parallax and primary proper motion were also calculated: 2.1, 2.2, 4.5 mas (mas/y). These separate errors have not been calculated in the previous

simulations of the nominal mission, but they may be estimated rather accurately from the available 'total' rms, which is about 1.36 mas. Using Lindegren's 'coefficients of improvement' for the different astrometric parameters, this translates to expected rms-values 1.55, 1.46 and 2.00 mas(mas/y). The present 'nominal' 24-month runs give 1.5, 1.5 and 3.1.

With observations for 18 months, the standard solution (no a priori information in the final solutions) still works for most of the systems. For the a-series, one gets 94 good solutions, for the b-series (with 'poor' a priori data) 83. It is clearly advantageous, however, to weakly constrain the solutions to the a priori values for the absolute and relative proper motions and the relative parallax. The constraint should be weak: instead of the $w(xk)$ used in PSSOL (cf. NDAC/LO/103) I have tested values 0.1 and 0.01 times $w(xk)$ and found the lower value clearly preferable. Such a weak constraint does not appreciably bias the solutions, but it helps greatly to prevent gross errors. With the constraint, one gets 100(a) and 92(b) good solutions. The rms primary position error is 4.4 mas, the rms parallax error 3.4 mas, and the rms primary proper motion error 10.8 mas/year. (The latter figure should be compared with the a priori figure about 70 mas/year used in the constraining).

With only 12 months of observations, it is (surprisingly?) possible to make unconstrained solutions for more than 60% of the systems. It is better to use again a weak constraint as for the 18-months runs, and then 82(a),77(b) good solutions are obtained. These are remarkably high figures, but the solutions are of course of definitely lower quality. The rms primary position error is now about 10 mas, the rms parallax error about 11 mas, and the rms primary proper motion error about 26 mas/year. (There is thus still some improvement even in the a priori poor proper motions).

3. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the present runs is that the procedures developed for the treatment of known binaries in the nominal mission are useable also in the recovery mission. Rough estimates of the percentage of systems with 'good' solutions and of the corresponding mean errors are given in Table 1 as a function of the mission duration.

Table 1. Estimated solution-results at different mission durations (n stands for the nominal geostationary orbit). nfov is the mean number of FOV-passages, and the rms-values are for the primary component (units mas and mas/year).

Dur.(mon)	nfov	% success	rms(pos)	rms(par)	rms(p.m)
30n	148	100	1.6	1.5	2.0
24n	118	96	1.5	1.5	3.1
24	77	96	2.1	2.2	4.5
18	57	96	4.4	3.4	11
12	36	80	10	11	26

Although these figures are based on a small number of simulations, they show conclusively the trend with the mission duration. Even a 12-month mission will give useable positions for a large number of the doubles, while an 18-month duration will give interesting parallaxes also.